

HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE CAUSES, SYMPTOMS, CLASSIFICATION, TREATMENT.

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Annatatsiya. High blood pressure or hypertension is one of the most common diseases of the cardiovascular system today. The disease is manifested by an increase in arterial blood pressure, and often its indicator exceeds 140/90.

According to many experts in the field of cardiovascular diseases, hypertension often occurs as a result of blood circulation disorders. Heart failure is also included in the list of its causes. This disease can trigger the development of secondary diseases in patients, for example, stroke, heart attack.

Keywords: Hypertension disease, Signs and symptoms of high blood pressure, Causes of hypertension, What is a hypertensive crisis, Diagnosis of hypertension, Stages of hypertension, Treatment of high blood pressure.

ВЫСОКОЕ КРОВЯНОЕ ДАВЛЕНИЕ ПРИЧИНЫ, СИМПТОМЫ, КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ, ЛЕЧЕНИЕ.

Аннагация. Повышенное артериальное давление или гипертония – одно из самых распространенных заболеваний сердечно-сосудистой системы на сегодняшний день. Заболевание проявляется повышением артериального давления, и нередко его показатель превышает 140/90.

По мнению многих специалистов в области сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний, гипертония часто возникает в результате нарушения кровообращения. Сердечная недостаточность также входит в список ее причин. Это заболевание может спровоцировать развитие у больных вторичных заболеваний, например, инсульта, инфаркта.

Ключевые слова: Гипертоническая болезнь, Признаки и симптомы повышенного артериального давления, Причины гипертонической болезни, Что такое гипертонический криз, Диагностика гипертонической болезни, Стадии артериальной гипертензии, Лечение гипертонической болезни.

INTRODUCTION

ABOUT HYPERTENSION DISEASE. Hypertension is a disease caused by a violation of the nervous-functional activity of blood vessels. The disease mainly occurs in people over 40 years old, but in recent years, it has been observed more often in young people. Both men and women suffer from hypertension. This disease is one of the leading causes of death among people with diseases of the cardiovascular system.

Scientists have been studying this disease for several decades. According to research, hypertension is one of the main causes of disability on our planet. According to statistics, if first aid is provided late when blood pressure increases, the condition of patients may worsen, and even death may occur.

SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS OF HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE

The main symptom of hypertension is headache due to spasm and narrowing of cerebral vessels. Also, noise in the ears, decreased visual acuity, weakness, sleep disturbances, dizziness, heaviness in the head, and increased heart rate are often manifested. These symptoms are

noticeable in the early stages of the disease. Later, heart failure occurs due to long-term straining of the heart.

In addition, many patients have the following symptoms:

1. Easy nosebleeds;
2. Return;
3. Insomnia;
4. Memory impairment;
5. Redness of the skin surface after any physical activity;
6. Strong pressure in the eyes (the patient feels pain in the eyes when looking around, so they prefer to rest and keep their eyes closed);
7. Rapid heartbeat;
8. Swelling in tissues;
9. Fatigue.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The reason for the development of the disease is long-term stress and depression, frequent psychological stress. Often these are caused by work that requires constant emotional tension. In addition, concussion patients have a high risk of developing the disease. Hereditary predisposition is also among the reasons: if a person's generation has this disease, then the risk of developing this disease increases several times.

The main factor affecting the development of the disease is a sedentary lifestyle. As people age, atherosclerosis can develop, and an increase in blood pressure against the background of this change makes the situation even more serious. This is extremely dangerous for life, because through narrowed blood vessels, it is observed that the blood does not flow to the brain, heart, or part of the kidneys. If there are thrombus and cholesterol accumulations on the walls of blood vessels, they can break off during strong pressure, clog the capillary blood vessels, and prevent blood flow. In this case, myocardial infarction or stroke occurs.

Hormonal changes during menopause can cause high blood pressure in women. Salt, or more precisely, the sodium contained in it, as well as smoking, alcohol abuse, and obesity also put pressure on the cardiovascular system.

In general, the factors influencing the development of hypertension include:

- Overweight, metabolic diseases, endocrine diseases, sedentary lifestyle;
- Experiencing regular emotional stress, depression, tragic events, loss of loved ones;
- Strong nervous tension due to problems in business, work;
- Brain injuries (car accident, fall, hypothermia);
- Chronic diseases that have a negative effect on the cardiovascular system (diabetes, gout, rheumatoid arthritis);
- Hereditary predisposition;
- Viral and infectious diseases (meningitis, sinusitis, sinusitis);
- Age-related changes in blood vessels;
- A high level of cholesterol in the blood, as a result of which accumulations are formed on the walls of blood vessels;
- Menopausal women over 40 years old (hidden diseases often develop during significant hormonal changes in the body and may affect the development of hypertension);

- Harmful habits (smoking, drinking alcoholic beverages, excessive coffee consumption);
- Eating a lot of salt during the day;
- Increase of adrenaline in the blood;
- Sitting in front of the computer for a long time;
- Little walking in the open air, etc.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Hypertensive crisis is a manifestation of the peak of the disease. In this case, blood pressure rises quickly, all the above-mentioned symptoms are observed, in addition, patients experience nausea, vomiting, sweating, and darkening of the eyes. Such crises can last from several minutes to several hours. Heart beat accelerates significantly, fear and excitement appear in the patient. In this case, the cheeks become red, the control of urine and feces is lost. Hypertensive crisis often occurs in the afternoon or evening.

Another type of hypertensive crisis develops over a long period of time, and it can torment the patient for 4-5 hours or even several days. This condition is manifested in the last stages of the disease and occurs against the background of an increase in arterial blood pressure. At this time, the patient's brain activity, in particular, speech and sensitivity in the hands and feet decrease.

DISCUSSION

DIAGNOSIS OF HYPERTENSION. In order to accurately diagnose the patient, the doctor will need to conduct several laboratory analyzes and hardware tests. The purpose of the diagnosis is to determine the stage of the disease and the degree of hypertension. With this information, the doctor will be able to choose an effective treatment method.

Since the early stages of the disease are hidden, most patients visit the doctor late. It is very difficult to completely cure the disease, so patients need to be patient, because the disease can accompany them for the rest of their lives. Therefore, it is necessary to prevent the disease in time, and if suspicious symptoms appear, it is necessary to undergo a doctor's examination.

At home, everyone should regularly measure their blood pressure, the most optimal indicator is 120/80 mm Hg (referred to below as a unit), 130/90 for adults. Pressure can increase by 5-10 units as a result of environmental influence or physical activity. A very large difference between the lower and upper pressure is also a sign of air pollution - usually this indicator should not exceed 50 units. If there are frequent changes in blood pressure, it is recommended to see a doctor.

PHASES OF HYPERTENSION

Modern medicine distinguishes 3 stages of arterial hypertension:

- Stage 1 — Blood pressure is in the range of 140-159 / 90-99 mm Hg. Blood pressure can periodically return to normal and rise again;
- 2nd stage — Blood pressure is in the range of 160-179 / 100-109 mm Hg. Arterial blood pressure often rises and rarely falls to normal.
- 3rd stage — pressure 180/110 mm wire. rises above The pressure is constantly high, and its decrease is caused by heart diseases.

TREATMENT OF HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE

A doctor qualified in the treatment of the disease chooses a course of drug treatment for each patient individually. In most cases, the following drugs are prescribed:

Thiazide diuretics — these drugs reduce fluid levels in the body and, as a result, lower blood pressure;

Sartans (angiotensin II receptor blockers) — have been used since the 1990s. Among the modern drugs, it keeps the blood pressure at a normal level for 24 hours after a single dose;

Calcium antagonists are prescribed when cardiac anomalies, arrhythmias, angina pectoris and cerebral atherosclerosis are observed;

Beta-adrenoblockers - normalize heart rhythm;

Alpha-adrenoceptor blockers - dilate blood vessels very carefully.

It is recommended that patients avoid any stress or emotional stress during treatment. Patients are recommended to walk in the open air: around the pool, in the garden, in the forest. Proper nutrition is important in the successful treatment of hypertension.

CONCLUSION

First of all, it is necessary to exclude products containing "bad" cholesterol and a large amount of salt from the daily diet. To them:

- Fatty meat;
- Charvy;
- Fried foods;
- Smoked products;
- Pickles are included.

It is useful to eat bread that has been standing for a day or two instead of fresh bread taken from the oven. It is necessary to include in the daily diet more products rich in servitamins and minerals that help fight against diseases. To them:

- Vegetables;
- Fruits;
- Berries;
- Greens;
- Dairy products;
- Dietary meat;
- Bean;
- Rice, buckwheat, etc.

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